

A COUPLE-STRESS/CAUCHY MULTISCALE MODEL FOR THE NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF PERIODIC MASONRIES UNDER IN-PLANE LOADING CONDITIONS

Lorenzo Leonetti¹, Fabrizio Greco², Patrizia Trovalusci¹, Raimondo Luciano³, and
Renato Masiani¹

¹ Department of Structural and Geotechnical Engineering, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
Via A. Gramsci, 53, 00197, Rome, Italy
e-mail: {lorenzo.leonetti, patrizia.trovalusci, renato.masiani}@uniroma1.it

² Department of Civil Engineering, University of Calabria, Italy
Via P. Bucci, Cubo 39B, 87036, Rende, Italy
e-mail: f.greco@unical.it

³ Department of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, University of Cassino and Southern Lazio, Italy
Via Di Biasio, 43, 03043, Cassino, Italy
e-mail: luciano@unicas.it

Keywords: Couple-Stress Model, Multiscale Multi-Domain Techniques, Masonry, Homogenization, Nonlinear analysis.

Abstract. *Concurrent multiscale approaches are suitable for studying the behavior of micro-structured materials, since they combine the advantages of both macroscopic and microscopic approaches, i.e. the computational efficiency and the numerical accuracy, respectively. These models, which are based on a domain decomposition approach, have been recently employed also for the failure analysis of masonry structures, in the framework of the (Cauchy-based) first-order homogenization schemes. In the present work, an enhanced multiscale strategy for the nonlinear analysis of periodic masonries is proposed, based on the adoption of a couple-stress model at the macroscopic scale. This model, which can be regarded a constrained version of the Cosserat model, has been proved to capture the size effects usually experienced by these heterogeneous materials. On the other hand, a classical Cauchy model is employed at the microscopic scale, where damage phenomena are modelled by introducing cohesive interfaces at mortar joints. The proposed multiscale model is equipped with an adaptive strategy able to zoom-in automatically the zones affected by damage initiation; this strategy requires the determination of microscopically derived first failure surfaces in the space of the couple-stress macrostrains. The validity of the proposed multiscale approach is assessed by performing numerical simulations for different masonry panels subjected to complex in-plane loading conditions. In addition, suitable comparisons with direct numerical simulations are proposed.*

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, multiscale methods have been used to predict the mechanical response of micro-structured materials, since they combine the advantages of purely macroscopic (i.e. computational efficiency) and microscopic models (i.e. numerical accuracy) [1–12]. These methods have been applied also to simulate the damage phenomena in masonry structures under complex loading conditions [13–17]. In this context, the most common strategy consists in deriving the overall nonlinear response via the so-called local-global approaches (see [13]). However, such a strategy ceases to be effective in the presence of severe localization.

As an alternative to the well-established local-global approaches, the concurrent multiscale methods have been also recently applied to the damage analysis of masonry structures [14,15]. These methods, relying on the concept of scale embedding, can be considered as a multilevel version of well-known domain decomposition methods.

Encouraged by the results obtained using these methods, we propose an enhanced multiscale model for the nonlinear analysis of periodic masonries under in-plane loading conditions. The main novelty of the present model is the exploitation of a couple-stress based micromechanical approach instead of a classical Cauchy first-order one, for deriving both the homogenized elastic moduli (in the linear range) and the first failure surface of masonry.

2 THEORETICAL FORMULATION

At a conventionally defined microscopic level, a brick masonry structure is here defined as a 2D composite body made of units and mortar joints, occupying a bounded open set $\Omega \subset R^2$. Its external boundary, denoted as $\partial\Omega$ and assumed to be Lipschitz-continuous, is made of two disjoint parts, i.e. $\partial_D\Omega$ and $\partial_N\Omega$, where Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions are imposed, respectively. Moreover, $\partial_D\Omega$ has nonzero measure in order to avoid any arbitrary rigid-body motions. The units are assumed undamageable and made of linearly elastic material, whereas the mortar joints, modeled as zero-thickness cohesive interfaces Γ_c placed in between the units, are assumed damageable according to a mixed-mode softening constitutive law. Even in the quasi-static setting, assuming negligible body forces and small deformations, the mechanical response of a masonry structure subjected to general loading conditions can be found by solving a highly complex nonlinear boundary value problem.

In order to reduce the complexity of such a purely microscopic model, a multiscale strategy is proposed in this work, based on a two-level domain decomposition technique used in conjunction with a couple-stress based homogenization technique. The key idea consists in adopting a homogenized model for masonry everywhere, except for critical regions, here collectively referred as *zone of interest*, where a certain first failure criterion is reached.

Therefore, the original problem is replaced by an equivalent multiscale multi-domain problem. The domain Ω is partitioned in two non-overlapping subsets Ω_M and Ω_m . Ω_M is the macroscopic subdomain, on which the homogenized moduli are assigned, whereas Ω_m denotes the microscopic subdomain, representing the zone of interest, for which all the structural details are explicitly accounted for. The resulting micro-to-macro interface is denoted as Γ_{int} .

2.1 Microscopic modeling of masonry

In the present model, all the nonlinearities are assumed to occur only within the zone of interest, thus requiring in this region a detailed microscopic modeling. To this end, the units are modeled by bulk elements whereas the behavior of mortar joints is lumped into zero-thickness interface elements. It is worth recalling here that units are assumed to be unbreakable.

Therefore, all the mortar joints are equipped with an intrinsic cohesive law of a mixed-mode type, involving a scalar state variable indicating the current interface damage level. A

modified version of the cohesive law described in [18] is used here, where an additional compressive cap is introduced. The elastic and inelastic material parameters of mortar joints are: normal, K_n , and tangential, K_s , elastic stiffness parameters, tensile, f_t , and shear, c , cohesive strengths, (masonry) compressive strength, f_c , friction angle, ϕ , and both mode-I, G_{Ic} , and mode-II, G_{IIc} , fracture energies. The elastic stiffness parameters of the interface have a precise physical meaning according to the approach followed in [19].

2.2 Macroscopic modeling of masonry

A couple-stress homogenization scheme is adopted to derive the overall behavior of the undamaged masonry [20]. After defining a repeating cell (see Fig. 1a), five different microscopic BVPs are solved, corresponding to three Cauchy and two bending macro-deformation modes (see Fig. 1b). Periodic fluctuations are applied for Cauchy deformation modes, whereas special mixed boundary conditions are imposed for the bending deformation ones [21,22].

Figure 1: Couple-stress homogenization: (a) repeating cell; (b) pure macroscopic deformation modes.

Due to the assumed orthotropic nature of the masonry microstructure, only six overall elastic moduli have to be identified via the proposed Cauchy/Couple-Stress homogenization. The complete homogenized constitutive law for masonry written in matrix form reads as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{11} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{22} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{12} \\ \bar{\mu}_{31} \\ \bar{\mu}_{32} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{1111} & \bar{A}_{1122} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{A}_{1122} & \bar{A}_{2222} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{A}_{1212} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{3131} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{3232} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_{11} \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_{22} \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_{12} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{31} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{32} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\kappa}_{31}$ and $\bar{\kappa}_{32}$ are the bending curvatures, $\bar{\mu}_{31}$ and $\bar{\mu}_{32}$ the couple-stresses, \bar{C}_{3131} and \bar{C}_{3232} the bending moduli characterizing the couple-stress macro-continuum behavior.

3 DESCRIPTION OF THE MULTISCALE SIMULATION ALGORITHM

In this section, the proposed multiscale simulation algorithm is described. Such an algorithm belongs to the class of *adaptive model refinement* methods. The key feature of the proposed adaptive model refinement algorithm consists in replacing the homogenized coarse-scale model by the original fine-scale model after a zooming-in criterion is satisfied, in an automatic matter. Such a criterion is a first failure criterion for the homogenized masonry.

This criterion requires the construction of the *first failure locus*, formulated for a periodic masonry subjected to arbitrary quasi-static loading paths, initially proposed for a Cauchy mac-

ro-continuum (see [14,15]) and here extended to a couple-stress model. Such a locus is defined for a given masonry repeating cell, as the set of macroscopic strain states corresponding to the microscopic crack onset in the most stressed point along the cohesive interfaces.

4 NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS: THE SHEAR WALL TEST

In this section, the proposed couple-stress based adaptive multiscale strategy has been validated, with reference to the failure analysis of a masonry wall subjected to a shear test [23].

4.1 Description of the test specimen and the boundary conditions

The test specimen here employed for validation purposes is the small-sized wall shown in Fig. 2. Its dimensions are $L = 980$ mm and $H = 1106$ mm, with a resulting width-to-height ratio of about one. The loading history is made of two steps. In the first one, a confinement is applied by prescribing a top vertical displacement until a compressive stress of 0.30 MPa is reached. In the second one, a top horizontal displacement is monotonically increased.

Figure 2: Masonry wall subjected to a shear test: geometry and boundary conditions.

The wall is made of bricks of $210 \times 52 \times 100$ mm³ periodically arranged according to a classical running bond. The thickness of mortar joints is set as 10 mm. The elastic behaviors of both brick and mortar materials are assumed linearly elastic and isotropic, whose material constants are listed in Table 1. The inelastic parameters taken from [24] are used (see Table 2).

Component	E [MPa]	ν [-]
Brick	16,700	0.15
Mortar	782	0.14

Table 1: Elastic material properties of bricks and mortar joints.

f_t [MPa]	c [MPa]	f_c [MPa]	ϕ [deg]	G_{Ic} [N/mm]	G_{IIc} [N/mm]
0.25	0.35	10.5	36.9	0.018	0.125

Table 2: Inelastic material parameters of mortar joints.

4.2 Results of the multiscale numerical simulation (MNS)

As a preliminary step, the homogenized moduli for the given masonry have been derived under the assumption of plane stress state, as explained in Section 2.2.

The first failure surface has been also derived. In practice, several (linear) microscopic problems have been solved for different macroscopic strain directions, each of which is associated with a critical point of this locus. A given critical point represents the macrostrain state corresponding to the occurrence of the first nonlinearity at mortar joints.

The results of the multiscale numerical simulation (MNS) are shown in terms of load-displacement curve. These results are compared with those coming from a direct numerical simulation (DNS), here considered as the reference ones, and from some experimental data found in the literature (see Fig. 3). The proposed multiscale methodology is able to obtain a structural response which is almost superposed to that resulting from the DNS. Moreover, the carrying capacity of masonry is well predicted, as confirmed by the very small percentage error on the peak load between the two analyses (less than 1%).

Finally, the computational performances exhibited by the proposed multiscale algorithm have been investigated. In detail, the CPU time ratio between MNS and DNS is of about 47%, corresponding to a significant speed-up value.

Figure 3: Comparison in terms of force vs displacement curve among multiscale numerical simulations (MNS), direct numerical simulation (DNS), and experiments by Rajmakers and Vermeltoort [23].

5 CONCLUSIONS

A Couple-Stress/Cauchy multiscale strategy has been proposed for performing complete nonlinear analyses of periodic masonries under in-plane loading conditions. Such a strategy relies on a two-scale domain decomposition method, used in combination with an adaptive model refinement technique which is able to automatically zoom the masonry zones undergoing microscopic damage initiation.

The main novelty of the present work consists in using as zooming-in criterion a microscopically derived first failure criterion for the homogenized masonry in the framework of couple-stress elasticity.

The present multiscale model has been suitably validated by applying it in numerically deriving the overall mechanical response of a masonry wall subjected to a shear wall test. The results obtained via the multiscale numerical simulation (MNS) have been compared with those coming from both a direct numerical simulation (DNS) and experiments found in the literature. The MNS has been found to predict very accurately both the peak and the post-peak responses. In detail, the error on the peak load has been found to be very small.

Encouraged by the present numerical results, future directions could concern the investigation of the so-called size effects in masonry structures. In detail, the incorporation of a characteristic length via the proposed couple-stress homogenized model should be able to predict the different behaviors exhibited by small- and large-sized masonries.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by Italian Ministry of University and Research (P.R.I.N. 2015, Sapienza and Calabria Research Units) and by Sapienza University Grant 2016.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y.W. Kwon, D.H. Allen, R. Talreja, *Multiscale modeling and simulation of composite materials and structures*. Springer, 2008.
- [2] F. Feyel, J.L. Chaboche, FE multiscale approach for modelling the elastoviscoplastic behaviour of long fibre SiC/Ti composite materials. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, **183**(3), 309-330, 2000.
- [3] S. Ghosh, K. Lee, P. Raghavan, A multi-level computational model for multi-scale damage analysis in composite and porous materials. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **38**(14), 2335-2385, 2001.
- [4] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, P. Lonetti, A two-scale failure analysis of composite materials in presence of fiber/matrix crack initiation and propagation. *Composite Structures*, **95**, 582-597, 2013.
- [5] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, P. Lonetti, P. Nevone Blasi, Crack propagation analysis in composite materials by using moving mesh and multiscale techniques, *Computers and Structures*, **153**, 201-216, 2015.
- [6] L. Feo, F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, Mixed-mode fracture in lightweight aggregate concrete by using a moving mesh approach within a multiscale framework, *Composite Structures*, **123**, 88-97, 2015.
- [7] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, A multiscale model for the numerical simulation of the anchor bolt pull-out test in lightweight aggregate concrete, *Construction and Building Materials*, **95**, 860-874, 2015.
- [8] V. Sansalone, P. Trovalusci, F. Cleri, Multiscale modeling of materials by a multifield approach: Microscopic stress and strain distribution in fiber–matrix composites, *Acta Materialia*, **54**(13), 3485-3492, 2006.
- [9] D. Capecchi, G. Ruta, P. Trovalusci, From classical to Voigt's molecular models in elasticity, *Archive for History of Exact Sciences*, **64**(5), 525-559, 2010.
- [10] P. Trovalusci, M.L. De Bellis, M. Ostoja-Starzewski, A. Murralli, Particulate random composites homogenized as micropolar materials, *Meccanica*, **49**(11), 2719-2727, 2014.

- [11] P. Trovalusci, M. Ostoja-Starzewski, M.L. De Bellis, A. Murrall, Scale-dependent homogenization of random composites as micropolar continua, *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids*, **49**, 396-407, 2015.
- [12] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, P. Nevone Blasi, Effects of microfracture and contact induced instabilities on the macroscopic response of finitely deformed elastic composites, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **107**, 233-253, 2016.
- [13] T.J. Massart, R.H.J. Peerlings, M.G.D. Geers, An enhanced multi-scale approach for masonry wall computations with localization of damage, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **69**, 1022-1059, 2007.
- [14] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, P. Nevone Blasi, An adaptive multiscale strategy for the damage analysis of masonry modeled as a composite material, *Composite Structures*, **153**, 972-988, 2016.
- [15] F. Greco, L. Leonetti, R. Luciano, P. Trovalusci, Multiscale failure analysis of periodic masonry structures with traditional and fiber-reinforced mortar joints, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **118**, 75-95, 2017.
- [16] P. Trovalusci, R. Masiani, Non-linear micropolar and classical continua for anisotropic discontinuous materials, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **40**(5), 1281-1297, 2003.
- [17] P. Trovalusci, A. Pau, Derivation of microstructured continua from lattice systems via principle of virtual works: the case of masonry-like materials as micropolar, second gradient and classical continua, *Acta Mechanica*, **225**(1), 157-177, 2014.
- [18] A. Lisjak, G. Grasselli, A review of discrete modeling techniques for fracturing processes in discontinuous rock masses, *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, **6**(4), 301-314, 2014.
- [19] P.B. Lourenco, J.G. Rots, Multisurface Interface Model for Analysis of Masonry Structures, *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, **123**(7), 660-668, 1997.
- [20] S. Forest, D.K. Trinh, Generalized continua and non-homogeneous boundary conditions in homogenisation methods, *ZAMM - Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics*, **91**(2), 90-109, 2011.
- [21] D. Addessi, M.L. De Bellis, E. Sacco, Micromechanical analysis of heterogeneous materials subjected to overall Cosserat strains, *Mechanics Research Communications*, **54**, 27-34, 2013.
- [22] X. Yuan, Y. Tomita, T. Andou, A micromechanical approach of nonlocal modeling for media with periodic microstructures, *Mechanics Research Communications*, **35**, 126-133, 2008.
- [23] T.M.J. Raijmakers, A.T. Vermeltoort, *Deformation controlled tests in masonry shear walls - report B-92-1156*, Technical Report, Delft, The Netherlands: TNO-Bouw, 1992.
- [24] P.B. Lourenco, *Computational strategies for masonry structures*, Doctoral Thesis, Delft University Press, 1996.